

Table 2. Varietal means for percent elongation at various water depths.

Variety	Elongation (%)						Variety mean
	80 cm	90 cm	100 cm	110 cm	120 cm	Control (no water)	
<i>Nonelongating dwarf</i>							
BKNFR76106	7.9 h	7.5 e	9.2 d	11.4 e	7.7 f	2.8 b	7.8
IR42	18.4 fg	16.6 d	21.3 c	17.9 de	10.8 hi	3.7 ab	14.8
<i>Nonelongating tall</i>							
IR28273-R-R-R-29-38-2-3-3	13.9 gh	8.2 e	13.5 d	12.0 e	18.0 fgh	7.9 ab	12.3
NDGR207	34.5 bc	25.1 c	27.7 c	32.8 c	19.0 efg	4.0 ab	13.9
<i>Elongating MV</i>							
IR11141-6-1-4	25.9 de	23.9 c	24.8 c	18.1 de	23.2 def	5.4 ab	20.2
IR11288-B-B-69-1	21.4 ef	19.7 ed	28.7 c	15.1 e	15.4 gh	9.1 ab	16.8
IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-2	19.9 efg	22.5 cd	28.0 c	24.7 d	17.8 fgh	9.9 b	19.5
Bhatin	32.6 cd	40.7 a	38.3 b	35.9 bc	32.3 bc	4.5 ab	30.7
LMN111	48.0 a	44.8 a	48.4 a	37.4 bc	25.8 cde	9.4 ab	35.6
<i>Fast elongating</i>							
Baisbish	38.6 bc	41.3 a	41.8 a	50.3 a	35.6 ab	2.9 ab	36.2
Barogar	40.5 b	33.9 b	45.8 a	41.8 b	29.8 bcd	9.1 ab	33.5
Kalaungi	37.3 bc	32.5 b	51.5 a	42.1 b	41.8 a	10.9 a	36.0
Depth mean	28.2	26.4	31.5	28.3	23.1	6.1	23.9

DWR seedlings. We classified 12 varieties as nonelongating dwarf, nonelongating tall, elongating modern variety (MV), elongating tall, and fast elongating. Plants were raised in 5-cm-

deep plastic pots, having 5-cm² surface area. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Five water depths were in the main plots and the 12 entries were in the subplots.

Elongation of deepwater rice during horizontal orientation of shoots in shallow water

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Elongating and nonelongating varieties were grown in three sets in completely randomized block design with three replications in tanks at IRRI. Plants were spaced at 30 cm with 90 cm between rows to prevent plants from shading each other. Elongated internode number was <1 and length <5 cm for all varieties at the beginning of the treatments.

In the first set of experiments, the water level was raised to 50 cm 6 wk after seeding. The tank was full at this level. A horizontally placed iron bar was used to submerge all leaves that were above the water. The bar was moved across the top of the tank 2-3 times/wk to stimulate kneeling and to keep plants

completely submerged as they grew. By the end of the experiment, the bar had been moved about 60 cm from the initial position. Using this procedure, all plants, including nonelongating varieties, were submerged but stayed alive.

The second set of the varieties were maintained in an upright position (URP) in 50 cm water and the third set was used as control without deep water treatment. Internode number and length were recorded on 10 randomly selected plants/replication from the three treatments.

Varieties in the horizontally placed (HP) treatment differed significantly in internode length (Table 1), with highest values recorded in Jalmagna, Baisbish, and NDGR417 followed by NDGR150, IR111288-B-B-69-1, and NDGR207 (Table 2). Internode length was minimum for IR42 and IR36. A similar trend in internode length occurred in URP treatment (Table 2). However, HP plants

We submerged 3-wk-old seedlings in a concrete tank where water depths of 80, 90, 100, 110, and 120 cm were maintained using a stair arrangement. Water depth was measured from the soil surface of the pots to the water surface. Percent elongation was calculated.

Varieties differed significantly in percent elongation at various water depths (Table 1). Elongation rate was greatest in Baisbish, Kalaungi, LMN111, and Barogar at almost all water depths. IR11141-6-1-4 and IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-2 showed moderate elongation (Table 2).

We recorded relatively more elongation at 100 cm for floating and DWR varieties. The overall percent elongation, irrespective of variety, was also highest (31.5%) at the 100 cm water depth. For genetic studies, 100 cm of water appears to be deep enough to test for elongation ability at an early stage.

The trend for decreasing elongation at 100 and 120 cm water depths may be due to the inability of plants to emerge from these depths. Alternatively, other adverse factors may exist that affect the ability of plants to elongate in deep water (120 cm) but not in shallow water (80-100 cm). Lower light irradiance could be one factor; this requires further experimentation. ■

had significantly greater internode length relative to those in URP (Table 2) and the control. NDGR207 elongated similarly under both treatments, possibly because of its tall but relatively nonelongating nature.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for internode length (cm) and number of internodes.

Sources of variation	DF	Mean sum of squares ^a	
		Internode length (cm)	Internodes (no.)
Treatment	26	2756.8**	11.3**
Main factor (M)	2	2940.2**	46.3**
Subfactor (S)	8	8014.1**	21.3**
M × S	16	105.3**	1.9**
Error	54	29.9	0.3
CV (%)		7.1	8.1

** = significant at 1% level.

Table 2. Length and number of internodes in horizontal placement (HP) and upright position (URP) of shoots in water at 50 cm depth.^a

Variety	Length of internodes (cm)				Elongated internodes (no.)				Elongation score in >100 cm water ^b (from previous test)
	Control	HP	URP	Difference (HP-URP)	Control	HP	URP	Difference (HP-URP)	
<i>Floating rice</i>									
Jalmagna	97 a	134 a	101 a	33**	7.0 a	11.7 a	7.7 a	4.0**	1
Balsbish	78 c	109 b	87 b	22**	6.0 b	11.0 a	7.0 ab	4.0**	1
NDGR417	88 b	111 b	101 a	10**	6.0 b	9.0 b	6.7 bc	2.3**	1
<i>Elongating modern variety</i>									
NDGR150	60 d	79 c	68 c	11*	5.0 cd	7.0 b	5.3 d	1.7**	5
IR11141-6-1-4	38 e	58 d	39 d	19**	6.0 b	7.3 c	6.3 b	1.0**	5
IR11288-B-B-69-1	42 e	62 d	50 d	12**	5.7 bc	7.3 c	6.0 bc	1.3**	5
<i>Traditional deepwater</i>									
NDGR207	61 d	62 c	65	-3 ns	4.3 de	6.7 c	4.3 e	2.4*	5
<i>Nonelongating modern variety</i>									
IR36	26 f	43 e	28 f	15*	4.0 e	5.0 d	4.0 e	1.0**	9
IR42	21 f	37 e	25 c f	12*	4.0 e	5.0 d	4.0 e	1.0**	9
Av	57	77	62	15	5.3	7.8	5.8	2.0	
Comparison 2-M*S mean									
LSD (0.05)	7.63	0.83							
LSD (0.01)	10.16	1.11							

^a*, ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively; ns = not significant. In a column, figures followed by different letters significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

The greater total internode lengths in HP treatments may be due to a more severe treatment when the submergence bar is moved 60 cm, relative to the 50-cm water depth increase in the URP treatment. This is consistent with the number of internodes from horizontally oriented shoots, which was greater than for URP plants.

Among the floating rices, plants in HP produced 9-12 internodes and those in the URP produced 7-8 internodes. The elongation scores of these varieties evaluated at >1-m water depth at Ghagharaghat, India, were comparable to those of HP shoots (data not presented).

The findings indicate that the horizontal orientation method sufficiently induced elongation and can be used to test plants for elongation potential. An advantage of this method is that deep flooding is not needed to test for internode elongation so it can be used to screen varieties or segregating populations. These benefits will need to be evaluated with respect to the greater surface area required for horizontal placement of plants. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Chlorophyll fluorescence analysis (CFA) for assessing cold tolerance at anthesis in Nepalese indigenous rice genotypes

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We screened eight rice genotypes (seven indigenous and one exotic) from the Himalayan region for sterile-type cold tolerance at anthesis using CFA (see table). The objective was to determine whether chlorophyll fluorescence, measured after a short period of chilling at the critical booting stage, would correlate with spikelet sterility.

During the process of photosynthesis, chlorophyll fluorescence is re-emitted from the chlorophylls associated with the

Cold tolerance ranking of rice cultivars at Pokhara, Nepal.

Variety	Altitude (m asl)	Field ranking for cold tolerance ^a	Origin
Chhomrong	1400-2000	CT at all growth stages	Nepal
Silange	1500-1800	CT at all growth stages	Nepal
Seto Takmare	1500-1700	CT at reproductive phase	Nepal
Rato Darmali	1600-1700	CT at late anthesis stage	Nepal
Kalopatle	1400-1500	CT at reproductive phase	Nepal
Bhatte	1200-1500	CWT at vegetative phase	Nepal
China 1039	1000-1200	CT at late anthesis stage	India
Marshi	900-1200	CS at all growth stages	Nepal

^aCT = cold tolerant, CWT = cold water tolerant, and CS = cold sensitive.